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STUDY OF SYMPTOMS, RISK FACTORS AND PRESCRIBING PATTERNS IN STROKE PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: Stroke or cerebrovascular accident is an acute focal neurological deficit that lasts for 24 hours due to disturbances in cerebral blood flow. It is a medical emergency which occurs commonly in elderly patients. According to WHO, 15 million people worldwide suffer from stroke each year. In India, the incidence of stroke is 145/100,000 per year during 2003-06. One in six people suffer from stroke in their lifetime. Our present study assesses the risk factors, symptoms and prescribing patterns for the better choice of one drug over the other. **METHODS:** A prospective study was conducted in the medicine department of Viswabharathi Hospital, Kurnool, AP. Required demographic and laboratory data, along with general neurological evaluation and brain CT was analyzed. **RESULTS:** In our study, the incidence of ischemic stroke (83%) was more when compared to hemorrhagic stroke (29%). Prevalence of disease was high in the age group of 56-65. Males are mostly affected than females due to risk factors like hypertension (61%), diabetes (28%), smoking (21%), alcohol (16%). Anti-coagulants (78%) were most commonly used drugs, whereas neurotrophics are least commonly used drugs (6%). **CONCLUSION:** The present study emphasizes on the need to identify risk factors and providing awareness among the patients by a pharmacist in minimizing the disease burden. It also points to the rationality in prescribing of drugs based on therapeutic guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION

An acute neurological deficit that lasts for 24 hours due to cerebral flow disturbances is known as stroke or cerebrovascular accident. Worldwide it causes major mortality, it is leading cause of death next to cancer and causes medical emergency commonly in elder patients.[1]

TYPES OF STROKES:[2]

1. Ischemic stroke: accounts for 87 percent of all stroke cases. Obstruction within the blood vessel supplying blood to the brain leads to ischemic stroke. Development of fatty deposits lining the vessel wall are the underlying conditions for this type of obstructions, the condition is also called as atherosclerosis. 1.) cerebral thrombosis 2.) cerebral embolism are the two types of obstructions caused due to fatty deposits.
2. Hemorrhagic stroke: occurs due to a weakened blood vessel rupture. Aneurysms and arteriovenous malformations (AVMS) are the two types which causes hemorrhagic stroke. Uncontrolled hypertension is the most common cause of hemorrhagic stroke.
3. Transient ischemic attack: TIA is also called as “mini stroke”, which is caused due to temporary clot.

CLINICAL PRESENTATIONS:

1. Sudden severe headache due to injury or other causes.
2. Vision change in the both the eyes or one that occurs suddenly.
3. Loss of coordination/balance or problem in walking and quick onset of dizziness
4. Problem in talking or expressing words
5. Numbness or weakness in arm, leg or face.

RISK FACTORS:

Borderline hypertension including hypertension, high levels of alcohol. Cigarette smoking, physical inactivity, cardiac morbidity, alcohol consumption are highly related to stroke risk factors. Homocysteine levels and high cholesterol levels in blood also lead to stroke.[4]

TREATMENT:

NICE and royal college of physicians set the current management pathway for acute stroke summarized in figure 1: [5,6,7]

Figure 1 The current management pathway set out by NICE and the Royal college of Physicians for acute stroke.

According to WHO, 15 million people worldwide suffer from stroke each year. In India, the incidence of stroke is 145/100,000 per year during 2003-06. One in six people suffer from stroke in their lifetime. The mortality rate due to stroke in India is 22 times that of malaria and 1.4 times that of Tuberculosis. Approximately 780,000 new and recurrent strokes occur annually in the US [1]. Several population-based surveys on stroke were conducted from different parts of India. During the last decade, the age-adjusted prevalence rate of stroke was between 250-350/100,000. Recent studies showed that the age-adjusted annual incidence rate was 105/100,000 in the urban community of Kolkata and 262/100,000 in a rural community of Bengal. The ratio of cerebral infarct to hemorrhage was 2.21. Hypertension was the most important risk factor. Stroke represented 1.2% of total deaths in India. [8]

The prevalence of the disease is very much closely related to its risk factors, categorized as fixed risk factors: age, gender, race, previous vascular event (MI, stroke, PVD), hereditary (high fibrinogen) and modifiable risk factors: blood pressure, cigarette smoking, hyperlipidemia, heart disease (atrial fibrillation, congestive cardiac failure, infective endocarditis), diabetes mellitus, excessive alcohol intake, estrogen-containing drugs [9].

Morbidity and mortality related to ischemic stroke can be concentrated by its prevention. 50% of stroke is preventable by control of modifiable risk factors and life style modifications like aerobic exercise to counteract inactivity, weight loss in obesity, glucose control in diabetics, smoking cessation and diet [10]. American stroke association (ASA) and American heart association (AHA) have recently published updates guidelines for secondary prevention of stroke [10].

METHEDODOLOGY:

Aim:
The present aim of the study is to provide a comprehensive review on gender differences in stroke, with specific stress on the demographics, risk factors, symptoms, prescribing patterns.

Objective:

- The objective of this study is to work out about the symptoms, risk factors and assessment of the prescribing patterns [1]
- To identify the choice of one drug over the other and about the changes made when stroke occurs in patient by the neuro physician [1].

Study site: this study was conducted in in-patient set up of medicine department of viswabarathi hospital, which is 250 bedded tertiary care teaching hospital providing health care service.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients diagnosed with ischemic, hemorrhagic stroke
- Male and female of age 5 years and above were included in study
- Patients who are alcoholic and non alcoholic
- Patients who are smoker and non smoker
- Patients data which were collected from case sheets and laboratory reports were included

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who are pregnant/lactating women
- Patients with hepatic disorders
- Only symptoms that were definitely present were counted, suspected and attainable weren't taken into consideration

Sample size:

After patient admission, 100 patients were selected and data was collected. The collected prescriptions were entered into Microsoft office excel sheet according to their age, gender, therapeutic category, and prescription and was approved by the institutional human ethics committee and informed consent from patients was taken.

Study location:

A prospective study was conducted in the medicine department of viswabarathi hospital; which is 250 bedded tertiary care teaching hospital providing health care services.

Study population:

A total of 100 cases were collected in which 90 cases were taken into consideration based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Method of study:

- A prospective study was conducted in the medical department of viswabarathi hospital; which is 250 bedded tertiary care teaching hospital providing health care service.
- The study was conducted in in-patient department in which the data regarding patients was collected.
- Totally 100 cases were collected in which the demographic details, complaints, type of stroke, treatment given, any past medical and medication history were collected.
- Out of 100 cases 90 cases were taken into consideration based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- The collected data was entered into Microsoft office excel sheet.
- The study is approved by the institutional human ethics committee and informed consent from patients was taken.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

TABLE 1: DATA OBTAINED ABOUT PATIENT DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERS (GENDER).

GENDER	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
Males	64	71%
Females	26	29%

FIGURE 1:

Males are prone to stroke conditions than females which might be due to risk factors like alcohol, cigarette smoking and most common risk factors like diabetes and hypertension.

TABLE 2: TYPE WISE CHARACTERIZATION OF STROKE PATIENTS.

TYPE OF STROKE	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
ischemic stroke	75	83%
hemorrhagic stroke	15	17%

FIGURE 2:

Among the data collected in this article individual with ischemic stroke are more in number when compared with hemorrhagic stroke. Percentage of ischemic stroke is about 83% and hemorrhagic stroke is about 17%.

TABLE 3: AGE WISE CATEGORIZATION OF STROKE PATIENTS.

AGE	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
05-15	1	1
16-25	2	2
26-35	4	4
36-45	4	4
46-55	17	19
56-65	32	36
66-75	12	13
76-85	18	20

FIGURE 3:

Out of 90 patients, maximum numbers of cases were collected in the age group of 56-65 with percentage of 36%.

TABLE 4: PATTERN OF SYMPTOMS AMONG STROKE PATIENTS.

SYMPTOMS	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
Headache	28	31 %
Giddiness	22	25 %
weakness of right upper and lower limb	15	16 %
weakness of left upper and lower limb	21	23 %
weakness of both rt and lt limbs	8	8 %
disoriented speech	23	25 %
deviation of mouth	14	15 %
facial palsy	8	8 %
blurred vision	6	6 %
vomitings	14	15 %
altered sensorium	3	3 %

FIGURE 4:

In the data collected most of people were present with symptoms like headache and giddiness with the percentage of 31% and 25% and least commonly seen with the symptoms like vomitings and altered sensorium with the percentage of 15% and 3%.

TABLE 5: PATTERN OF RISK FACTORS AMONG STROKE PATIENTS.

RISK FACTORS	NO.OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
alcoholic	15	16
smoking	19	21
alcoholic and smooking	5	5
hypertension	55	61
diabetes	26	28
recurrent stroke	13	14
cad	1	1
ckd	1	1
epilepsy	1	1

FIGURES5:

In above collected data commonly seen risk factors were hypertension and diabetes followed by smoking and alcoholic with the percentage of 61%, 28% ,21%, 16% , and cad , ckd, epilepsy were seen in 1%.

TABLE 6: PATTERN OF DRUGS GIVEN TO STROKE PATIENTS.

DRUGS	NO. PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
Atorvastatin	62	69 %
Aspirin	53	59 %
Cloidogrel	51	56 %
Citicoline	47	52 %
Mannitol	43	47 %
Telmisartan	23	25 %
Labetalol	19	21 %
Amlodipine	19	21 %
Enaxoparin	18	20 %
Clonazepam	16	17 %
hydrochlorthiazide	13	14 %
cerebroprotein hydrolysate	6	6 %
Alprazolam	4	4 %
Rosuvastatin	4	4 %
Haloperidol	3	3 %
Nifedipine	3	3 %

FIGURE 6:

In the collected data most commonly prescribed drugs were atorvastatin and aspirin in the percentage of 69% and 59% and least prescribed drugs were haloperidol and nifedipine in the percentage of 3%.

TABLE 7: PATTERN OF DRUGS IN STROKE PATIENTS ACCORDING TO THEIR CLASS.

DRUGS	NO.OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE%
anticoagulants	71	78 %
antiplatelets	51	56 %
dyslipidaemic agents	66	73 %
psycho stimulants	47	52 %
osmotic diuretics	43	47 %
angeotensin receptor blockers	23	25 %
calcium channel blockers	22	24 %
beta blockers	19	21 %
benzodizepines	20	22 %
thiazide diuretics	13	14 %
nootropics	6	6 %

FIGURE 7:

Anti coagulants and dyslipidemic agents were most commonly prescribed drugs in the sample followed with antiplatelets and psychostimulants with the percentage of 78%, 73%, 56% and 52%.

TABLE 8:

Type Of Therapy	No.Of Patients	Percentage
Combination Therapy	88	97.7
Single Therapy	2	2.3

FIGURE 8:

DISCUSSION

In our study the incidence of ischemic stroke is more than the hemorrhagic stroke. Mostly effected age group was (56-65) which was comprised of 35% followed by the age group of (76-85) which was comprised of 20%. In our study males are more affected to stroke than females which comprises of 71% and females of 29%. Study by sangram vurumadla et al also suggests that stroke events were more in males than in females [11].

In our study out of total study population 75 patients i.e., (83%) experienced ischemic stroke and 26 patients i.e., (29%) experienced hemorrhagic stroke. This explains the prevalence of ischemic stroke is more than hemorrhagic stroke due pathophysiological changes.

Males are more prone to ischemic stroke than females due to smoking and alcohol and presence of risk factor hypertension and diabetes.

Out of total number of patients 31% of patients were present with the symptom of headache, 25 % of patients were presented with symptoms of giddiness and disoriented speech, 23% of patients were experienced with the symptom of weakness of left upper limb and lower limb, 16% of patients were experienced with the symptom of weakness of right upper and lower limb, 15% patients were experienced with symptoms of deviation of mouth and vomitings, 8% of patients were experienced with symptoms of facial palsy and weakness of both upper and lower limbs, 6% of patients with blurred vision and 3% with altered sensorium.

Among 90 patients most commonly observed risk factor was hypertension in 61% followed with diabetes in 28%, smoking 21% and alcohol 16%. Patients with both alcohol and smoking were in percentage of 5. Recurrent stroke was observed in patients with percentage of 14%. And the remaining CAD, CKD, epilepsy were in the percentage of 1%.

Most commonly used class of drugs was anticoagulants (78%), dyslipidemic agents (73%), antiplatelets (56%), psychostimulants (52%), osmotic diuretics (47%), ARB'S (25%), CCB's (24%), benzodiazepines (22%), beta blockers (21%), thiazide diuretics (14%), nootropics (6%).

The most commonly used drugs were: Atorvastatin (62), Aspirin (53), Clopidogrel (51), Citicoline (47), Mannitol (43) According to Sridhar srinath et al most commonly used drugs were antiplatelets and psychostimulants where as in this study the most commonly used drugs were anti coagulants and dyslipidemic agents [1].

Most commonly used combination therapy was atorvastatin and clopidogrel. Total no of patients with single therapy are 2 (2.3%) and with combination therapy are 99 (97.7%).

CONCLUSION

Out of 90 patients whose details are collected, maximum numbers of cases were in the age group of 56-65 years. The incidence of stroke was higher in males than in females the most commonly observed type of stroke was ischemic stroke. The most commonly seen symptom was headache followed by giddiness and disoriented speech. Hypertension and diabetes were main risk factors observed in the study followed by smoking and alcohol and the commonly prescribed drugs to patients were of the class anticoagulants and dyslipidemic agents in which the drugs were aspirin, enoxaparin and atorvastatin. The present study emphasizes on the need to identify risk factors and providing awareness among the patients by a pharmacist in minimizing the disease burden. It also points the rationality in prescribing of drugs based on therapeutic guidelines.

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